

Standardization of Variables for Dyeing Cotton Fabric with Five Synthesized Reactive Dyes

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Received: April 26, 2014, Accepted: May 18, 2014, Published: May 20, 2014.

ABSTRACT

This study presents standardization of dyeing variables for dyeing of five synthesized reactive dyes (Red A, Red B, Red C, Orange D and Black BE) on 100 % cotton fabric. These dyes contained sulfo vinylsulfone functionality and were prepared by either reacting cyanuric chloride with H-acid and coupling with the diazotized product of sulfo vinylsulfone/sulfo tobiaz acid or reacting diazotized sulfo vinylsulfone with H-acid/sodium naphthionate under optimized conditions. Different variables which affect the process of dyeing like dye concentration, dyeing temperature, pH of dyeing solution, dyeing time and concentration of auxiliaries used during dyeing were systematically evaluated. All measurements were made at wavelength maxima (λ_{max}) of respective dyes Red A (540 nm), Red B (535 nm), Red C (530 nm), Orange D (520 nm) and Black BE (630 nm). The results showed that 3 % dye concentration was adequate for maximum dye absorption on the cotton fabric and 1 % was ideal for fastness to sunlight and wash. The optimized values for other variables were, dyeing temperature: 80 °C, pH of dyeing: 11.0, drying time: 90 min; and 80/85 g/L of sodium chloride and 20/25 g/L of sodium carbonate as auxiliaries for 1 % and 3 % dye concentration respectively.

Keywords: *Reactive dyes; Cotton fabric; Standardization; Optimization; Dyeing variables*

INTRODUCTION

Reactive dyes are the leading choice of colorants that are used for colouring cotton goods. They are the only class of dyes which makes covalent bond with the fiber molecules and find wide applicability due to broad colour range and superior colour fastness. Majority of the wet possessing industries use reactive dyes for dyeing of textiles [1]. The dyeing of fabric is one of the key processes in the successful trading of textile products. Nevertheless, the process of dyeing is complex and requires careful optimization and control of several variables for reproducible results. These include type/nature of fabric, concentration of dye, pH of dyeing, temperature, dyeing time and concentration of auxiliaries used during the dyeing process [1-3]. Any variation in these parameters can directly impact colour fastness to light and washing.

The first reactive dyes, Procion M dyes were introduced for cotton fabric by ICI [4]. These dyes contain a highly reactive dichlorotriazinyl group, which reacts with cellulose fiber at room temperature in the presence of an alkali. Further, other dyes with

lower reactivity containing monochlorotriazinyl which required hot dyeing were developed. Additionally, remazol dyes considered as warm dyes possessing vinyl sulphonyl group were first marketed by Hoechst [5, 6]. Presence of both vinyl sulphone and monochlorotriazine reactive groups in the same dye molecule allows higher fixation of the dye on the fabric in the temperature range of 60-80 oC [5]. Hot dyeing was used by Taylor [5] and Bae et. al. [7] for monochlorotriazine reactive dye and a good colour yield was obtained when dyed at 80 oC. Furthermore, the type and concentration of auxiliaries added during dyeing of reactive dyes is one of the key variables which can impact the exhaustion of the dyes. Alam et al. [8] and Farha et. al. [9] reported that the uptake of dye increased when electrolytes were added to the dye liquor of anionic dye. Singla and co-workers [3] standardized different dyeing variables of reactive red H dye for tie and dye on cotton fabric. In the present work, an attempt is made to standardize important dyeing variables like dye concentration, dyeing temperature, pH of dyeing solution, dyeing time and concentration

of auxiliaries for superior colour fastness on cotton fabric using five synthesized reactive dyes (Red A, Red B, Red C, Orange D

and Black BE). The chemical structures of these dyes are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Chemical structure of synthesized reactive dyes

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and chemicals

Reactive Red A, Reactive Red B, Reactive Red C, Reactive Orange D, Reactive Black BE were synthesized with purity $\geq 98\%$. The synthesis of Red A, Red B and Red C has been reported earlier [10, 11]. Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3), sodium chloride (NaCl), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium lauryl benzene sulfonate and ammonium perchlorate were of commercial grade. Commercially available cotton fabrics (plain weave, 36's warp and 30's weft, yarn density 72/inch warp and 69/inch weft) were dried at about 100°C for over 6 h after de-sizing with ammonium perchlorate, NaOH and sodium lauryl benzene sulfonate [12].

Instrumentation and conditions

The centrifuge machine LCEN-101 used was from MRC Labs International. A digital EH1000 pH meter from Line Seiki (Japan) was employed for pH measurements. A Varian Cary 400 UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Palo Alto, CA, USA) with 10 mm

matched quartz cells was used to carry out UV absorption studies. Beckman DK-2A double-beam spectrophotometer (Maryland, USA) equipped with an Ulbricht sphere and powered by a hydrogen lamp was used to measure UV transmittance through the fabric samples. An SLI 440 dyeing machine (dye bath) manufactured by Sahas Laboratory Instruments (Ahmedabad, India) was used to dye the fabric samples.

Dyeing of cotton fabric and measurement of colour fastness

Dyeing of cotton fabric was carried out following the method described previously [11]. The performance of dyed cotton fabric for shade change/fastness was assessed against the International Geometric Grey Scales [13]. The values assigned for these properties were, 5 - Negligible change (Excellent), 4 - Slight change (Good), 3 - Noticeable change (Fairly good), 2 - Considerable changed (Fair), 1 - Enormous change (Poor).

Determination of optimum wave length of dyes

To determine the optimum wavelength, 0.2 % stock solutions of the dyes were prepared in deionized water. Dye solutions for absorption measurements were made at 0.004 % by appropriate dilution of the stock solutions. These solutions were scanned from 300 to 700 nm to find the wavelength corresponding to maximum absorbance.

Optimization of dyeing variables

To optimize dyeing conditions for reactive dyes, several variables like dye concentration, temperature, dyeing time, pH and concentration of dyeing auxiliaries on cotton fabric were studied as reported previously [3].

Dye concentration

For establishing the optimum dye concentration, eight different concentrations (1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0 and 8.0 %) of respective reactive dyes were taken and the fabric samples were dyed at 80-100 °C for 30 min with constant stirring using 60 g/L sodium chloride. To bring the pH of the solution to 11.0, sodium carbonate was added. Absorbance of the dye solutions were measured at their respective wavelengths before and after dyeing. The dye solution which gave the maximum dye absorption was selected as an optimum dye concentration for the respective dyes.

Dyeing temperature

To optimize dyeing temperature, dyeing was carried out using optimum concentration of dye at five different temperatures i.e. 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 °C. The optimum dyeing temperature was selected as the temperature which gave maximum absorption of dye on the fabric.

Dyeing time

The cotton samples were dyed using optimum dye concentration for five different time durations i.e. 80, 90, 100, 110 and 120 min and the optimum dyeing time was selected on the basis of maximum dye absorption.

Dyeing pH

To optimize the pH of dyeing, different pH ranging from 9.0-12 with an increment 0.5 of dyeing solutions were studied. The fabric samples were added to the solution and dyed under optimized conditions to find the most appropriate pH for dyeing.

Concentration of auxiliaries

Different concentrations of auxiliaries such as sodium chloride i.e. 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85 and 90 g/L and sodium carbonate i.e. 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 g/L were added in the dye bath. Optimum concentration of both the auxiliaries was decided on the basis of maximum dye absorption. Further, the number of installments of both the auxiliaries used was also optimized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The absorbance measurements of aqueous solutions of dyes were recorded from 300-700 nm and the absorption spectra for the dyes with the wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{max}) is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Absorption spectra of Reactive red A (λ_{max} 540 nm), Reactive red B (λ_{max} 535 nm), Reactive red C (λ_{max} 530 nm), Reactive orange D (λ_{max} 520 nm) and Reactive black BE (λ_{max} 630 nm) in deionized water.

a) *Optimization of concentration:* The results for optimization of concentration of dye for absorption are illustrated in Figure 3. It is clearly evident that 3.0 % dye concentration provided the maximum absorption for all the studied reactive dyes. The % dye absorption increased up to 3 % and thereafter decreased gradually till 8.0 %. This behavior can be understood by the fact that presence of excess dye in the dye bath hinders the absorption of the dye on the fabric. The same observation was also reported by two previous studies with reactive dyes [3, 8].

Figure 3 Optimization of concentration of five reactive dyes for maximum absorption on cotton fabric.

The results for colour fastness properties of the dyes are shown in Table 1. It is apparent that absorption of 1.0 % dye concentration gave superior results for colour fastness with an average score of 4.8 on the Grey Scale. All dyed fabric samples gave better shade and colour fastness with 1.0 % dye concentration. Singla et al. [3] showed that reactive dyes give good fastness properties on account of stable electron arrangement and covalent bond formation between the dye and fiber which provides good resistance to washing and sunlight. Thus, 1.0 and 3.0 % dye concentration were selected for optimization of other variables.

Table 1 Optimization of dye concentration for colour fastness based on Grey Scale

Dye conc. (%)	Reactive Red A	Reactive Red B	Reactive Red C	Reactive Orange D	Reactive Black BE
	Washing/Sunlight	Washing/Sunlight	Washing/Sunlight	Washing/Sunlight	Washing/Sunlight
1.0	5.0/5.0	5.0/4.0	5.0/4.0	5.0/5.0	5.0/5.0

2.0	5.0/4.0	5.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	5.0/4.0	5.0/4.0
3.0	5.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	5.0/4.0	5.0/4.0
4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0
5.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0
6.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0
7.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0
8.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0	4.0/4.0

Figure 4 Optimization of temperature for maximum absorption of 1% and 3% concentration of reactive dyes on cotton fabric.

b) *Optimization of dye temperature:* Dyeing temperature is crucial for dye absorption and fixation on the fabric. For optimizing

dyeing temperature, five different temperatures i.e. 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 °C were studied using 1.0 and 3.0 % dye concentration.

Figure 4 shows % dye absorption-temperature profiles for all five dyes. Maximum absorption was possible at 80 °C with subsequent decrease in absorption up to 100 °C and thus was selected as optimum dye temperature for both the dye concentrations.

c) *Optimization of dyeing time:* Dyeing time can be defined as the time required getting the dye fixed on fabric at an optimum temperature. In the present work 80, 90, 100, 110 and 120 min were evaluated as dyeing time for standardization. The percent

dye absorption at different dyeing time employing optimum dye concentration and dyeing temperature are given in Table 2. It is apparent that maximum dye absorption for 1.0 and 3.0 % dye concentrations was observed at 90 min of dyeing time. The dye absorption decreased beyond this time, possibly due to stripping of dye on account of saturation of dye bath and hence 90 min was selected for further optimization of dyeing variables.

Table 2 Optimization of dyeing time for reactive dyes at 80 oC.

Time (min)	Dye absorption (%)									
	Reactive Red A		Reactive Red B		Reactive Red C		Reactive Black BE		Reactive Orange D	
	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %
80	63.23	73.54	42.65	50.11	41.43	47.34	71.54	80.20	71.77	85.00
90	67.12	74.45	47.45	53.12	43.78	52.44	73.23	84.33	74.98	87.88
100	65.43	71.77	45.34	49.32	39.54	47.11	70.11	77.56	72.00	82.89
110	60.77	69.15	39.21	46.12	37.34	42.09	65.65	71.54	67.11	77.67
120	55.12	65.22	30.22	36.65	28.65	33.21	56.11	62.98	56.80	68.77

Figure 5 Variation in dye absorption with pH for 1.0 and 3.0 % concentration of reactive dyes on cotton fabric at 80 oC with dyeing time of 90 min.

d) *Optimization of pH of dyeing*: The pH of dyeing solution significantly impacts the shade and the extent of dye absorption. The dye absorption at different pH values for 1.0 and 3.0 % dye concentrations at 80 °C are illustrated in Figure 5. For both the dye concentrations, maximum absorption was found at pH 11.0 and hence was selected as optimum dyeing pH.

d) *Optimization of concentration of auxiliaries for dyeing*: In the present study, different concentrations of sodium chloride and sodium carbonate were taken as auxiliaries. Sodium chloride was used as an electrolyte and exhausting agent and sodium carbonate

was added for the control of pH. Both the auxiliaries were taken in two equal installments for better colour absorption. Singla et al. [3] reported the use of sodium sulphate as an electrolyte to suppress the negative charge build-up at the fiber surface for dye up-take. The results obtained for 1.0 and 3.0 % dye concentrations with 30-90 % sodium chloride and 5-30 % of sodium carbonate are represented in Table 3. Based on these results 80/85 g/L of sodium chloride and 20/25 g/L of sodium carbonate as auxiliaries was optimized for 1 % and 3 % dye concentration respectively.

Table 3 Optimization of concentration of auxiliaries for dyeing of reactive dyes.

Sodium chloride (g/L)	Percent dye absorption at 80 °C for 90 min at pH 11.0									
	Reactive Red A		Reactive Red B		Reactive Red C		Reactive Black BE		Reactive Orange D	
	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %
60	54.22	64.11	31.42	35.02	27.44	32.88	55.00	61.88	54.99	67.75
65	58.11	69.10	37.99	45.33	35.77	41.27	64.11	71.05	65.76	76.55
70	61.78	68.89	38.11	45.99	36.22	41.99	64.55	74.33	66.55	80.00
75	62.90	73.21	40.99	47.00	37.12	43.22	67.21	76.99	68.22	81.33
80	68.44	75.95	46.44	54.22	42.99	51.33	72.44	83.32	74.50	86.98
85	64.22	76.11	44.54	55.22	40.22	52.00	69.41	84.46	71.90	87.00
90	61.00	74.54	41.45	51.33	37.22	46.11	67.95	79.10	70.00	84.67
Sodium carbonate (g/L)	Reactive Red A		Reactive Red B		Reactive Red C		Reactive Black BE		Reactive Orange D	
	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %	1 %	3 %
	5	65.88	75.88	42.10	52.21	38.33	40.11	68.44	75.00	69.18
10	66.10	76.22	44.22	46.00	41.22	47.22	71.44	77.99	71.12	80.90
15	68.20	77.11	45.54	49.22	44.17	49.14	74.33	80.22	73.22	84.43
20	72.11	78.53	50.12	53.44	46.18	50.22	76.33	83.22	77.11	87.20
25	68.12	79.22	48.22	56.11	44.11	54.30	73.48	84.88	74.19	89.22
30	66.54	77.90	45.13	55.38	42.17	52.89	71.90	82.5	72.13	88.01

CONCLUSION

Dyeing with reactive dyes on cotton fabric requires high levels of control over a range of variables especially for an exhaust dyeing condition. The present work highlights this criterion by standardizing critical parameters like dye concentration, dyeing temperature, pH of dyeing solution, dyeing time and concentration of auxiliaries for dyeing with five reactive dyes. The outcome of this study shows that 1.0 % dye concentration provides good fastness properties, while maximum dyeing takes place with 3.0 % dye concentration under the optimized conditions of dyeing temperature: 80 °C, pH of dyeing: 11.0, drying time: 90 min; and 80/85 g/L of sodium chloride and 20/25 g/L of sodium carbonate as auxiliaries for 1 % and 3 % dye concentration respectively.

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Citation: Mallika Sanyal, et al (2014) Standardization of Variables for Dyeing Cotton Fabric with Five Synthesized Reactive Dyes. *J. of Physical and Chemical Sciences*.VII3. DOI: 10.15297/JPCS.VII3.02

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